

Study Report

Analyzed File	simulacion13052022 v7
Version	Autodesk Fusion 360 (2.0.17457)
Creation Date	2023-11-02, 15:27:11
Author	elias

☐ Report Properties

Title	Estudios
Author	ingmi

Modelo de simulación 1:1

Estudio 1: OBJETO REPOSANDO EN PALMA

Study Properties

Study Type	Static Stress
Last Modification Date	2022-05-26, 16:40:11

Settings

General

Contact Tolerance	0.1 mm
Remove Rigid Body Modes	No

Damping

Mesh

Average Element Size (% of model size)	
Solids	10
Scale Mesh Size Per Part	No
Average Element Size (absolute value)	-
Element Order	Parabolic
Create Curved Mesh Elements	Yes
Max. Turn Angle on Curves (Deg.)	60
Max. Adjacent Mesh Size Ratio	1.5
Max. Aspect Ratio	10
Minimum Element Size (% of average size)	20

Adaptive Mesh Refinement

Number of Refinement Steps	0
Results Convergence Tolerance (%)	20
Portion of Elements to Refine (%)	10
Results for Baseline Accuracy	von Mises Stress

Materials

Component	Material	Safety Factor
SOCKET13052022 v3:1/Body9	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
SOCKET13052022 v3:1/Body7	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
PALMA v16:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/INDICE:1/PROXIMAL:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/INDICE:1/MEDIAL:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/INDICE:1/DISTAL:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEDIO:1/PROXIMAL (1):1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEDIO:1/DISTAL:2	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEDIO:1/MEDIAL:2	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/ANULAR:1/DISTAL:3	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/ANULAR:1/MEDIAL:3	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/ANULAR:1/PROXIMAL (2):1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEÑIQUE:1/DISTAL:4	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEÑIQUE:1/MEDIAL:4	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEÑIQUE:1/PROXIMAL (3):1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength

DedosOficial v21:1/PULGAR:1/DISTAL:5	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/PULGAR:1/ProximalP:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength

PLA OVERTURE

Density	1.25E-06 kg / mm ³
Young's Modulus	3980 MPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.332
Yield Strength	1 MPa
Ultimate Tensile Strength	49.5 MPa
Thermal Conductivity	2.98E-04 W / (mm C)
Thermal Expansion Coefficient	7.02E-07 / C
Specific Heat	2287 J / (kg C)

Contacts

Bonded

Name
[S] Bonded1 [DISTAL:5 ProximalP:1]
[S] Bonded2 [MEDIAL:4 PROXIMAL (3):1]
[S] Bonded3 [DISTAL:4 MEDIAL:4]
[S] Bonded4 [MEDIAL:3 PROXIMAL (2):1]
[S] Bonded5 [DISTAL:3 MEDIAL:3]
[S] Bonded6 [DISTAL:2 MEDIAL:2]
[S] Bonded7 [PROXIMAL (1):1 MEDIAL:2]
[S] Bonded8 [MEDIAL:1 DISTAL:1]
[S] Bonded9 [PROXIMAL:1 MEDIAL:1]
[S] Bonded10 [PALMA v16:1 ProximalP:1]
[S] Bonded11 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL (3):1]
[S] Bonded12 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL (2):1]
[S] Bonded13 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL (1):1]
[S] Bonded14 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL:1]
[S] Bonded15 [PALMA v16:1 ProximalP:1]
[S] Bonded16 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7) PALMA v16:1]
[S] Bonded17 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7) PALMA v16:1]
[S] Bonded18 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7)]
[S] Bonded19 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) PALMA v16:1]
[S] Bonded20 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7)]
[S] Bonded21 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7)]

Mesh

Type	Nodes	Elements
Solids	561362	379723

Load Case1

Constraints

Fixed1

Type	Fixed
Ux	Fixed
Uy	Fixed
Uz	Fixed

Selected Entities**Fixed2**

Type	Fixed
Ux	Fixed
Uy	Fixed
Uz	Fixed

Selected Entities**Loads****Gravity**

Type	Gravity
Magnitude	9.807 m / s ²
X Value	0 m / s ²
Y Value	-9.807 m / s ²
Z Value	0 m / s ²

Selected Entities

PROXIMAL

Type	Force
Magnitude	2 N
X Value	0 N
Y Value	-0.684 N
Z Value	1.879 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

Selected Entities

MEIDAL

Type	Force
Magnitude	2 N
X Value	0 N
Y Value	1.554 N
Z Value	1.259 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

Selected Entities

▣ **DEDOS**

Type	Force
Magnitude	2 N
X Value	0 N
Y Value	1.561 N
Z Value	-1.251 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

▣ **Selected Entities**

▣ **PALMA**

Type	Force
Magnitude	2 N
X Value	-3.782E-15 N
Y Value	-2 N
Z Value	1.173E-15 N
Force Per Entity	No

▣ **Selected Entities**

☐ Force11

Type	Force
Magnitude	1 N
X Value	0.7118 N
Y Value	-0.6545 N
Z Value	0.2548 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

☐ Selected Entities

☐ Force12

Type	Force
Magnitude	1 N
X Value	0.6529 N
Y Value	0.7172 N
Z Value	0.2438 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

☐ Selected Entities

Results

Result Summary

Name	Minimum	Maximum
Safety Factor		
Safety Factor (Per Body)	0.01532	15
Stress		
von Mises	1.946E-06 MPa	65.29 MPa
1st Principal	-28.57 MPa	76.24 MPa
3rd Principal	-74.38 MPa	37.29 MPa
Normal XX	-50.84 MPa	66 MPa
Normal YY	-51.29 MPa	50.2 MPa
Normal ZZ	-37.31 MPa	47.72 MPa
Shear XY	-27.07 MPa	35.14 MPa
Shear YZ	-17.08 MPa	14.82 MPa
Shear ZX	-15.77 MPa	22.27 MPa
Displacement		
Total	0 mm	0.4604 mm
X	-0.02665 mm	0.4141 mm
Y	-0.2433 mm	0.016 mm
Z	-0.01131 mm	0.1488 mm
Reaction Force		
Total	0 N	0.2092 N
X	-0.1907 N	0.05383 N
Y	-0.08445 N	0.1164 N
Z	-0.03885 N	0.05402 N
Strain		
Equivalent	6.865E-10	0.02885
1st Principal	-6.779E-08	0.02243
3rd Principal	-0.02945	1.159E-06
Normal XX	-0.007498	0.009445
Normal YY	-0.009058	0.003667
Normal ZZ	-0.003125	0.004314
Shear XY	-0.01812	0.02352
Shear YZ	-0.01143	0.00992
Shear ZX	-0.01056	0.01491
Contact Pressure		
Total	0 MPa	73.97 MPa
X	-20.27 MPa	67.17 MPa
Y	-16.78 MPa	37.37 MPa

Z	-13.95 MPa	29.99 MPa
Contact Force		
Total	0 N	6.265 N
X	-5.317 N	5.845 N
Y	-2.625 N	3.293 N
Z	-2.16 N	2.138 N

☐ Safety Factor

☐ Safety Factor (Per Body)

0 8

☐ Stress

☐ von Mises

[MPa] 0 65.29

☐ 1st Principal

[MPa] -28.57 76.24

☐ **3rd Principal**

[MPa] -74.38 37.29

☐ **Displacement**

☐ **Total**

[mm] 0 0.4604

☐ **Estudio 2:SUJETANDO OBJETO**

☐ **Study Properties**

Study Type	Static Stress
Last Modification Date	2022-05-26, 16:47:01

☐ **Settings**

☐ General

Contact Tolerance	0.1 mm
Remove Rigid Body Modes	No

☐ Damping

☐ Mesh

Average Element Size (% of model size)	
Solids	10
Scale Mesh Size Per Part	No
Average Element Size (absolute value)	-
Element Order	Parabolic
Create Curved Mesh Elements	Yes
Max. Turn Angle on Curves (Deg.)	60
Max. Adjacent Mesh Size Ratio	1.5
Max. Aspect Ratio	10
Minimum Element Size (% of average size)	20

☐ Adaptive Mesh Refinement

Number of Refinement Steps	0
Results Convergence Tolerance (%)	20
Portion of Elements to Refine (%)	10
Results for Baseline Accuracy	von Mises Stress

☐ Materials

Component	Material	Safety Factor
SOCKET13052022 v3:1/Body9	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
SOCKET13052022 v3:1/Body7	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
PALMA v16:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/INDICE:1/PROXIMAL:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/INDICE:1/MEDIAL:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/INDICE:1/DISTAL:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEDIO:1/PROXIMAL (1):1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEDIO:1/DISTAL:2	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEDIO:1/MEDIAL:2	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/ANULAR:1/DISTAL:3	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/ANULAR:1/MEDIAL:3	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/ANULAR:1/PROXIMAL (2):1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEÑIQUE:1/DISTAL:4	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEÑIQUE:1/MEDIAL:4	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/MEÑIQUE:1/PROXIMAL (3):1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/PULGAR:1/DISTAL:5	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength
DedosOficial v21:1/PULGAR:1/ProximalP:1	PLA OVERTURE	Yield Strength

☐ PLA OVERTURE

Density	1.25E-06 kg / mm ³
Young's Modulus	3980 MPa
Poisson's Ratio	0.332
Yield Strength	1 MPa
Ultimate Tensile Strength	49.5 MPa
Thermal Conductivity	2.98E-04 W / (mm C)

Thermal Expansion Coefficient	7.02E-07 / C
Specific Heat	2287 J / (kg C)

☐ Contacts

☐ Bonded

Name
[S] Bonded1 [DISTAL:5 ProximalP:1]
[S] Bonded2 [MEDIAL:4 PROXIMAL (3):1]
[S] Bonded3 [DISTAL:4 MEDIAL:4]
[S] Bonded4 [MEDIAL:3 PROXIMAL (2):1]
[S] Bonded5 [DISTAL:3 MEDIAL:3]
[S] Bonded6 [DISTAL:2 MEDIAL:2]
[S] Bonded7 [PROXIMAL (1):1 MEDIAL:2]
[S] Bonded8 [MEDIAL:1 DISTAL:1]
[S] Bonded9 [PROXIMAL:1 MEDIAL:1]
[S] Bonded10 [PALMA v16:1 ProximalP:1]
[S] Bonded11 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL (3):1]
[S] Bonded12 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL (2):1]
[S] Bonded13 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL (1):1]
[S] Bonded14 [PALMA v16:1 PROXIMAL:1]
[S] Bonded15 [PALMA v16:1 ProximalP:1]
[S] Bonded16 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7) PALMA v16:1]
[S] Bonded17 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7) PALMA v16:1]
[S] Bonded18 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7)]
[S] Bonded19 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) PALMA v16:1]
[S] Bonded20 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7)]
[S] Bonded21 [SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body9) SOCKET13052022 v3:1(Body7)]

☐ Mesh

Type	Nodes	Elements
Solids	561362	379723

☐ Load Case1

☐ Constraints

☐ Fixed1

Type	Fixed
Ux	Fixed
Uy	Fixed
Uz	Fixed

☐ Selected Entities

Fixed2

Type	Fixed
Ux	Fixed
Uy	Fixed
Uz	Fixed

Selected Entities

Loads

Gravity

Type	Gravity
Magnitude	-9.807 m / s ²
X Value	0 m / s ²
Y Value	9.807 m / s ²
Z Value	0 m / s ²

Selected Entities

PROXIMAL

Type	Force
Magnitude	2 N
X Value	0 N
Y Value	-0.684 N
Z Value	1.879 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

Selected Entities

MEIDAL

Type	Force
Magnitude	2 N
X Value	0 N
Y Value	1.554 N
Z Value	1.259 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

Selected Entities

▣ DEDOS

Type	Force
Magnitude	2 N
X Value	0 N
Y Value	1.561 N
Z Value	-1.251 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

▣ Selected Entities

▣ PALMA

Type	Force
Magnitude	-2 N
X Value	3.782E-15 N
Y Value	2 N
Z Value	-1.173E-15 N
Force Per Entity	No

▣ Selected Entities

Force11

Type	Force
Magnitude	1 N
X Value	0.7118 N
Y Value	-0.6545 N
Z Value	0.2548 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

Selected Entities

Force12

Type	Force
Magnitude	1 N
X Value	0.6529 N
Y Value	0.7172 N
Z Value	0.2438 N
X Angle	0 deg
Y Angle	0 deg
Z Angle	0 deg
Force Per Entity	No

Selected Entities

Results

Result Summary

Name	Minimum	Maximum
Safety Factor		
Safety Factor (Per Body)	0.0156	15
Stress		
von Mises	1.946E-06 MPa	64.12 MPa
1st Principal	-28.04 MPa	74.93 MPa
3rd Principal	-73.04 MPa	36.63 MPa
Normal XX	-49.93 MPa	64.86 MPa
Normal YY	-50.41 MPa	49.31 MPa
Normal ZZ	-36.63 MPa	46.85 MPa
Shear XY	-26.65 MPa	34.52 MPa
Shear YZ	-16.8 MPa	14.55 MPa
Shear ZX	-15.46 MPa	21.87 MPa
Displacement		
Total	0 mm	0.4519 mm
X	-0.02617 mm	0.4069 mm
Y	-0.2385 mm	0.016 mm
Z	-0.01105 mm	0.1452 mm
Reaction Force		
Total	0 N	0.6768 N
X	-0.6333 N	0.1378 N
Y	-0.2291 N	0.05816 N
Z	-0.208 N	0.2141 N
Strain		
Equivalent	6.865E-10	0.02833
1st Principal	1.055E-10	0.02204
3rd Principal	-0.02895	3.04E-07
Normal XX	-0.007365	0.009277
Normal YY	-0.008915	0.003602
Normal ZZ	-0.003066	0.004231
Shear XY	-0.01784	0.02311
Shear YZ	-0.01125	0.009736
Shear ZX	-0.01035	0.01464
Contact Pressure		
Total	0 MPa	72.69 MPa
X	-19.91 MPa	66.01 MPa
Y	-16.47 MPa	36.77 MPa

Z	-13.69 MPa	29.42 MPa
Contact Force		
Total	0 N	6.154 N
X	-5.224 N	5.741 N
Y	-2.568 N	3.231 N
Z	-2.121 N	2.1 N

☐ Safety Factor

☐ Safety Factor (Per Body)

0 8

☐ Stress

☐ von Mises

[MPa] 0 64.12

☐ 1st Principal

[MPa] -28.04 74.93

▣ **3rd Principal**

[MPa] -73.04 36.63

▣ **Displacement**

▣ **Total**

[mm] 0 0.4519

